

Effect of Responsiveness on the Sustainability of Food and Beverage Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State

Authored by

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Abstract

The study examined the effect of responsiveness on the sustainability of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state. The specific objectives were to: examine the effect of promptly and effectively addressing tasks on the sales increase; and evaluate the effect of timely communication on the market development of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state. The area of the study was Enugu state, Nigeria. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. The population of the study was seven hundred and twenty one (721) management and senior staff. The sample size of 251 was used using Ferund and Williams's formula at 5 percent margin of error. Two hundred and fourteen (214) staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Z - test statistic tool. The findings indicated Promptly and effectively addressing tasks had positive significant effect on the sales increase $Z(95, n = 214), 7.143 < 8.100, P. < .05$ and Timely communication had significant positive effect on the market development of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state $Z(95, n = 214), 5.195 < 7.690, P. < .05$. The study concluded that promptly and effectively addressing tasks and timely communication had significant effect on the sales increase and market development of food and beverage firms in Enugu State. The study Recommended among others that the management of food and beverage firms should try and break the workload into manageable chunks and setting priorities, as it will help break the cycle of missed deadlines, last-minute rushes, and procrastination.

Keywords: Sustainability; Food and Beverage Manufacturing Firms; Timely Communication; Market Development

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Introduction

Mindful organizations are often effective in their goal attainment and effectiveness, given their capacity for both in anticipating, and in containing, the unexpected. One way to anticipate the unexpected is preoccupation with failure, which implies attention to the small and large failures that may appear in an organization (Dagogo & Dublin, 2020). As such the capability to respond effectively advances the organizations chances of survival, within its current environment as well as its estimated placement in the future. Hence, organizational responsiveness can be described as comprising of the strategic as well as operational features. In the field of organizational realities, their elements and respective people are mutual 'respondents' or 'co-respondents' in a relationship, which is sensitive to differences as part of a formation process. Instead of calculated exchange, being responsive is a living practice of processing as an interactive give and take, which provides the base for re-interpreting responsibility. A phenomenological understanding of response and responsiveness is not limited to a behavioristic interpretation of a reactive response following causally from a stimulus. Phenomenologically, responsively comprises manifold interpretations of giving and receiving proactive reaction (Kupers, 2011).

A sustainable business requires a clear vision, a strategic alignment, and a continuous improvement of organization products, services, and processes. Responsiveness is the ability to listen, understand, and act on the needs and expectations of your customers, partners, and stakeholders. It is a key skill for building strong relationships and trust, which are essential for a sustainable business (Linked, 2023). Workplace responsiveness is the ability to communicate effectively and promptly with your colleagues, managers, and clients. It is a crucial interpersonal skill that can enhance reputation, productivity, and career advancement. Promptly addressing customer inquiries, providing clear and concise answers, and actively seeking feedback are effective strategies for being responsive to customers. Additionally, personalized communication and showing empathy can enhance the customer experience. Regularly updating customers on the status of their requests or issues also contributes to responsiveness (Okarter, 2024).

Responsiveness is a key to effective sales leadership. It is a key indicator of respect and commitment to customers, and It is also a key indicator of a sales leader's respect for and commitment to their team members. By embracing eco-friendly practices, not only can businesses reduce its carbon footprint, but it can also enhance customer loyalty and appeal to a growing base of environmentally-conscious consumers (Nedungadi, 2023). The survival of the societies and shared planet depends on a more sustainable world. Businesses around the world are increasingly taking responsibility for promoting sustainability by setting higher standards than required by applicable laws. The study seeks to evaluate

Statement of the Problem

A firm's success depends largely on its ability to build strong relationships with its customers, meet their expectations for quality service, and keep them satisfied with its products or services. The implementation of environmental responsiveness is a complex process that requires cross-functional coordination and substantial operational changes. The increasing and inefficient use of resources has knock-on effects including climate change, loss of biodiversity, pollution, poor health and poverty. These issues are interlinked and in turn often exacerbate each other.

A firm's organizational structure determines how employees from different levels interact, exchange information, and participates in decision making. Responsiveness in manufacturing firm is a key challenge for facing open-ended changes more and more enhanced by the increasing development of easy-to-use digital technologies. Implementing organizations responsive system often comes with a lot of challenges as a result of lack of prompt and effective addressing tasks and untimely communication of the organization managers.

The global business environment is so turbulent that products' life cycle shrinks easily and new ones are introduced. This makes flexibility and responsiveness to customers' demand inevitable. To overcome this complexity, organizations ought to device a means of overcoming these challenges as it has a high tendency of can decrease sales in the organization and as well decrease market development opportunities in the organization. In other to solve these challenges the study evaluates the effect of responsiveness on the sustainability of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate the effect of responsiveness on the sustainability of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Examine the effect of promptly and effectively addressing tasks on the sales increase of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state.
- ii. Evaluate the effect of timely communication on the market development of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formed for the study

- i. What is the effect of promptly and effectively addressing tasks on the sales increase of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state
- ii. What is the effect of timely communication on the market development of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state

Test of Hypotheses

The study made use of the following hypotheses

- i. Promptly and effectively addressing tasks has effect on the sales increase of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state
- ii. timely communication has effect on the market development of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Responsiveness

Responsiveness is a measure of how quickly and efficiently an organization responds to the needs of its customers. It is determined by assessing how quickly customer inquiries and complaints are answered and how effectively recommendations are implemented and feedback is received. Customer responsiveness can also refer to the speed and accuracy with which orders are filled. Responsiveness is essential for maintaining customer satisfaction and loyalty, as customers appreciate timely responses to their inquiries and feedback. Organizations must ensure that they have systems to monitor customer inquiries, respond to them promptly, and take appropriate action on any issues that may arise. Organizations typically use monitoring tools such as surveys, interviews, focus groups, or mystery shoppers to assess customer responsiveness levels (Experts, 2023). Responsiveness is a measure of a company's ability to react to and satisfy the needs of its customers. It is a key component of customer satisfaction, which is critical to every business's success. In short, customer responsiveness is a critical aspect of business survival and success (Nelson, 2022).

Components of Responsiveness used in the Study

Promptly and Effectively Addressing Tasks

A task is an individual job, a subset of one's responsible role. Task is a specific activity or piece of work that needs to be accomplished within a certain timeframe. It is a discrete, specific action that contributes to achieving a larger goal or objective (Quora, 2023). Task interdependence was rightly assumed to be exogenously determined by characteristics of the work and the technology.

Effectively carrying out the primary task of the organization serves as the ballast that ensures its survival. Effective task management skills are crucial for navigating the complexities of both personal and professional life. Managing tasks effectively at work is all about being organized, efficient, and proactive. It entails setting clear goals, identifying

and prioritizing tasks, creating a schedule, and monitoring progress. One of the key elements of managing tasks is setting clear goals, identifying and prioritizing tasks. This means identifying what needs to be done, why it needs to be done, and by when. This helps organizations stay focused and motivated, as well as provides a sense of direction and purpose for tasks (Reggie, 2022).

Timely Communication

Communication is the actionable transfer of information from one person, group, or place to another by writing, speaking, or using a medium that provides a means of understanding. Every communication consists of a minimum of one sender, a receiver, and a message. The transmission of a message from sender to recipient risks being affected by many things because communication impacts how people interact. These include the location, medium used to communicate, the cultural situation, and the emotions involved. However, communication helps people to interact and share various aspects of life (Ntara, 2023). Communication is the process of sending and receiving messages through verbal or nonverbal means, including speech, or oral communication; writing and graphical representations (such as infographics, maps, and charts); and signs, signals, and behavior. More simply, communication is said to be "the creation and exchange of meaning" (Nordquist, 2019).

Sustainability

In business, **sustainability** refers to doing business without negatively impacting the environment, community, or society as a whole. Sustainability means meeting the needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. In addition to natural resources, we also need social and economic resources. The goal of a sustainable business strategy is to make a positive impact on at least one of those areas. When companies fail to assume responsibility, the opposite can happen, leading to issues like environmental degradation, inequality, and social injustice (Spiliokos, 2018 & Eze, Olorunda & Mbah, 2022). In the broadest sense, sustainability refers to the ability to maintain or support a process continuously over time. In business and policy contexts, sustainability seeks to prevent the depletion of natural or physical resources, so that they will remain available for the long term (Mollenkamp, 2023; Agbo, Eze & Mbah, 2022).

Components of Sustainability used in the Study

Sales Increase

Sales Increase is the increase in sales of a product or service over time. It measures how well a business performs in terms of its revenue from sales. Sales growth can be measured by comparing the year-over-year, quarter-over-quarter, or month-over-month sales. The goal of any business should be to increase both unit and dollar sales growth simultaneously. This indicates that the company is not only selling more units but also commanding higher prices for them. Furthermore, measuring sales growth helps determine whether a business has the potential for long-term success since it shows that customer demand for the product or service is increasing (Experts, 2023). Sales Increase is the different between a company's sale at the beginning of the measurement period and such company's sales at the end of the measurement period, determined by the committee in its reasonable discretion (Lawinsider, 2024).

Market Development

Market development is a growth strategy that identifies and develops new market segments for current products. A development strategy targets non-buying customers in currently targeted segments. It also targets new customers in new segments. A market development strategy is a business growth strategy that focuses on introducing existing products to new markets (Indeed, 2023). Market development is a strategic step taken by a company to develop the existing market rather than looking for a new market. The company looks for new buyers to pitch the product to a different segment of consumers in an effort to increase sales (Economicstimes, 2024).

Theoretical Review

Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder theory is the theory used in this study to explain the motivation of firms that embark on responsiveness to enhance their sustainability. Freeman (2010) defined stakeholder as “any group or individual who can affect or is affected by the achievement of an organizations purpose”. Stakeholder theory has been articulated in a number of ways, but in each of these ways, stakeholders represent a broader constituency for corporate responsibility than stockholders. Stakeholder theory looks at the relationships between an organization and others in its internal and external environments. It also looks at how these connections influence their business conducts and activities. The original proposer of this theory is Edward Freeman and he recognized it as an important element of corporate social responsibility in his book, “Strategic Management: A Stakeholder’s Approach”. Freeman (1984) opined that the core idea of stakeholder theory is that organizations that manage their stakeholder relationships effectively will survive longer and perform better.

The term ‘Stakeholder’ includes a wide range of interest groups who are involved in organization. As part of management theory, and practice, stakeholder theory takes a number of forms. Descriptively, some research on stakeholder theory assumes that the operators who wish to maximize their firm’s potential will take broader stakeholder interest into account. As opined by Deegan, Rankin and Voght (2010), stakeholder theory can be divided into two branches: the ethical (moral) branch and a positive (managerial) branch. The ethical branch is based on the premise that “all stakeholders have the right to be treated fairly by an organization, and that managers should manage the organization for the benefit of all stakeholders”. This implies that all stakeholders have the rights to be provided with information about how a company’s activities influence them. The positive branch is based on the argument that organizations will respond to society through stakeholder power in order to influence Corporate Management. Based on this perspective, organization will produce information targeted to the concerns and expectations of specific groups or powerful stakeholders related to organization.

Stakeholder theory was used in this study to explain the relationship between responsiveness and the responsiveness of their sustainability.

Empirical Review

Promptly and Effectively Addressing Tasks on the Sales Increase

Odokoro, Uzuagu & Abanyam (2022), conducted a study on cooperate social responsibility and environmental sustainability strategies among SMEs in Enugu State. The study adopted descriptive research design. The population of the study was seventy-eight (78). Validated questionnaire was used for data collection. Mean and standard deviation were utilized for analyzing research question while ANOVA was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that the strategies used by SMEs in implementing CSR in Enugu State included ensuring safety of employees, adequate waste disposal management and prevention of waste pollutants to host communities. Findings also indicated that the strategies used by SMEs in implementing ES included ensuring that the business activities do not affect the natural environment, reducing pollutants in the environment, implementing green manufacturing practices such as waste reduction, reuse and recycling, among others. ANOVA showed that there was no significant difference in the mean responses of SMEs on the strategies used in implementing environmental sustainability.

Ede, Okolie & Aku-ibe (2023) conducted a study on the social processes and performance of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state. The specific objectives were to: examine the effect of gain commitment on the improved employee productivity and identify the effect of communication on the optimization of resources of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state. The area of the study was food and beverage firms in Enugu State. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 1238 selected staff of the study organizations. The adequate sample size of two hundred and ninety-three (293) using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error. Two hundred and fifty-seven (257) staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 88 percent response

rate. Data was presented and analyzed using Likert Scale and the hypotheses using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). The findings indicated Gain commitment had positive significance relationship with the improved employee productivity ($r = .424 < .983, p < .05$) and Communication had positive significance relationship with optimization of resources of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state ($r = .383 < .966, p < .05$). The study concluded that gain commitment and communication had positive relationship significance on the improved employee productivity and optimization of resources of food beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

Asogwa, Okechukwu, Nwoha, & Nwankwo (2023) conducted a study on the effect of firm productivity on the financial performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Nigeria from 2011 to 2020. The specific objectives of the study are: to ascertain the effect of sales growth, sales per employee, and profit per employee on return on assets of foods and beverage manufacturing firms in Nigeria. A sample of eight (8) firms was selected from the fifteen (15) foods and beverage manufacturing firms listed on Nigeria Stock Exchange during the period. The data collected from the selected firms were analyzed using multiple regression analysis and t-statistics. Results from the study showed that the effect of all the independent variables (sales growth, sales per employee and profit per employee) on the returns on assets of the foods and beverage manufacturing firms are positive and statistically significant. The implication of these findings is that as sales growth, sales per employee and profit per employee increase, the return on assets of the firms also increases and vice versa. Based on these findings the study recommended that the managers of foods and beverage manufacturing firms in Nigeria should increase their sales growth by increasing sales revenue in order to increase return on assets.

Igwe-Ukwurji, Orga & Mbah (2023). Conducted a study on how to study evaluate risk management strategy and performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The specific objectives of the study were to; examine the relationship between risk identification and the output and evaluate the relationship between risk reporting and reduces expenses of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 3123 staff of the organizations under study was used. To determine the adequate sample size of 213, the study used Freund and William's statistic formula at 5percent margin of error. Two hundred and fifty-six (256) returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. Data was presented and analyzed using Likert Scale and the hypotheses using Z-test. The findings indicated that Risk identification had significant positive relationship with the output $t(95, n = 256), 4.43 = p < 0.05$. Risk reporting had significant positive relationship with the expenses reduction of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State, $t(95, n = 256), 5.483 = p < 0.05$.

Didia, Akani & Ateke (2023) The purpose of this study is to investigate pricing strategies and sales force performance in food and beverages firms in Port Harcourt. The study employed a descriptive survey as its research design. The population of this study was twenty-three (23) registered food and beverages firms in Port Harcourt. The general manager, marketing manager, customer relationship manager and sales manager were the respondents drawn from each of these firms. The sample size was 93 food and beverages firms in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The Spearman's rank order was the test statistics. All statistical analysis was done using SPSS.23.0. The study found that pricing strategies positively and significantly influences sales performance of food and beverages firms in Port Harcourt. Based on the findings, the study therefore concluded pricing strategies significantly influences sales force performance of food and beverages firms in Port Harcourt.

Timely Communication on the Market Development

Nwonyuku (2016) conducted a study on the goal of a firm is to create sustainable profitability. And corporate governance should work to ensure this steady increase in corporate performance. Understanding the impact of corporate governance on firm profitability has warranted a special attention over time by different fields of scientific knowledge. This study was aimed to explore the relationship between corporate governance and profitability of firms, employing eight food and beverages firms listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange from 2004 to 2014. The data were analyzed using basic descriptive and inferential statistics with Ordinary Least Square multiple regression in a panel data setting. The results revealed that at 5 per cent level of significance, board size has positive relationship with return on equity and net assets per share. However, board composition has negative relationship with return on equity but with positive association with net assets per share. Board skills and competence has negative relationship with return on equity and net assets per share, while board gender diversity results indicated positive

relationship with return on equity and net assets per share. Despite the mixed results, it can be argued that the empirical results support the contention that corporate governance has a positive relationship with profitability of firms.

Onyeizugbe, et al. (2018) conducted a study on the non-existence of a pure state of industrial harmony, management practice of exclusionism, and derogation of organizational communication pattern among food and beverage firms in Anambra state have led to grievance between employees and management which has eroded the set objectives of these firms. This study seeks to determine the extent of relationship that exists between industrial harmony and employee performance in selected Food and Beverage Firms in Anambra state while specifically the study seeks to ascertain the extent of relationship that exists between joint consultation and employee engagement in selected Food and Beverage Firms in Anambra State, and to determine the extent of relationship that exists between industrial democracy and employee loyalty in selected Food and Beverage Firms in Anambra State. The study employed correlation survey research design. The population of the study was 390 employees of five selected Food and Beverage Firms in Anambra State, Pearson product moment correlation was used to analyze the data collected. The findings revealed that there is a very strong significant positive relationship between joint consultation and employee engagement, and there is a very strong positive relationship between industrial democracy and employee performance.

Njoku (2021) conducted a study on high failure rate of continuous improvement (CI) initiatives in the beverage industry. Continuous improvement initiatives could help beverage manufacturing managers improve product quality, efficiency, and overall performance. Grounded in the transformational leadership theory, the purpose of this quantitative correlational study was to examine the relationship between idealized influence, intellectual stimulation, and CI. Nigerian beverage industry managers (N = 160) who participated in the study completed the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire Form 5X-Short, and the Plan, Do, Check, and Act (PDCA) cycle. The results of the multiple linear regression were statistically significant, $F(2, 157) = 16.428$, $p < 0.001$, $R^2 = 0.173$. Idealized influence ($\beta = 0.242$, $p = 0.000$) and intellectual stimulation ($\beta = 0.278$, $p = 0.000$) were both significant predictors.

Ozioko (2021) conducted a study on the effect of technological environment on the administrative performance of public enterprises in Nigeria: Evidence from the Enugu State Housing Development Corporation (ESHDC), Enugu, South East Nigeria. This study adopted descriptive survey research in which pre-tested and well validated questionnaire was used to collect data from respondents who were selected from all the staff of the Enugu State Housing Development Corporation (ESHDC) under investigation. The population of the corporation was 875 and from this population, a sample of 268 was drawn using Cochran's finite population correction factor technique. The questionnaire comprised 15 closed-ended items set on the 5- point Likert-type scale. Results of the reliability test of the questionnaire showed it has a Cronbach's Alpha index of 0.84. The respondents were selected using purposive sampling method, which allowed selection of only the senior management staff of the parastatal who had good knowledge of the issues concerning technological environment of their organization. Descriptive statistics that consists of frequency, counts, tables and percentages was used to analyze the data as Multiple Regression Analysis was used in testing the hypotheses of the study. Both the analysis and tests were done with the aid of SPSS software. The findings of this study reviewed that technological invention and innovation have significant effect on the profit margin of ESHDC, Enugu; that automation has significant effect on the sales growth of ESHDC, Enugu; and that technological changes have significant effect on the number of beneficiaries of houses constructed by ESHDC, Enugu.

Ugwu, Eneh and Orga (2023) conducted a study on Corporate Culture defers from one organization to another and is a system of shared understanding or common beliefs held by members of the same organization. These common beliefs and shared understanding affect the performance and profitability of organizations. Hence, the study evaluated the effect of corporate culture on the profitability of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in South East Nigeria. The specific objectives were to: examine the effect of learning and development on the increase in revenue; evaluate the effect of communication on the change in productivity and determine the effect of trust on the reduced expenses. The study adopted descriptive survey. The primary source of data was questionnaire. A total population of three hundred and twenty two (312) staff was used. 273 staff returned the questionnaire. Data was analyzed and Z – test was used to test the hypotheses. Findings showed that Learning and development had positive effect on the increase in revenue, $Z(97, n = 273) = 6.582 < 9.547$. Communication had positive effect on the change

in productivity $Z(97, n= 273) = .7.006 < 7.671$. Trusts had positive effect on the reduced expenses $Z(97, n= 273) = .7.671 < 10.107$.

Methodology

The area of the study was Enugu state, Nigeria. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. The population of the study was seven hundred and twenty one (721) management and senior staff. The sample size of 251 was used using Ferund and Williams’s formula at 5 percent margin of error. Two hundred and fourteen (214) staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 85 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.800 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Z - test statistic tool.

Data presentation

The effect of promptly and effectively addressing tasks on the sales increase of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state

Table 1: Responses on the effect of promptly and effectively addressing tasks on the sales increase of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Being responsible improve work relationships and increase the number of sales.	470	268	57	16	26	837	3.91	1.331	Agree
		94	67	19	8	26	214			
		43.9	31.3	8.9	3.7	12.1	100%			
2	Enhancing professional performance promoted the growth of the business.	565	236	54	12	18	885	4.14	1.212	Agree
		113	59	18	6	18	214			
		52.8	27.6	8.4	2.8	8.4	100%			
3	Boosting the well-being at work enhanced contact of customers.	505	272	39	36	14	866	4.05	1.209	Agree
		101	68	13	18	14	214			
		47.2	31.8	6.1	8.4	6.5	100%			
4	Fulfilling commitments increased success in the business.	400	312	39	52	17	820	3.83	1.271	Agree
		80	78	13	26	17	214			
		37.4	36.4	6.1	12.1	7.9	100%			
	Learning from mistakes improved growth in revenue in the organizations.	435	320	39	24	22	840	3.93	1.272	Agree
		87	80	13	12	22	214			
		40.7	37.4	6.1	5.6	10.3	100%			
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.972	1.259	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1, 161 respondents out of 286 representing 75.2 percent agreed that being responsible improve work relationships and increase the number of sales 3.91 and standard deviation of 1.331. Enhancing professional performance promoted the growth of the business 172 respondents representing 80.4 percent agreed with mean score of 4.14 and standard deviation of 1.212. Boosting the well-being at work enhanced contact of customers 169 respondents representing 79.0 percent agreed with mean score of 4.05 and standard deviation of 1.209. Fulfilling commitments increased success in the business 158 respondents representing 73.8 percent agreed with mean score of 3.83 and 1.271. Learning from mistakes improved growth in revenue in the organizations 167 respondents representing 78.1 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.93 and standard deviation 1.272.

The effect of timely communication on the market development of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Responses on the effect of timely communication on the market development of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Prompt listening for information helps the business allocate resources.	460	296	39	20	25	840	3.93	1.316	Agree
		92	74	13	10	25	214			
		43.0	34.6	6.1	4.7	11.7	100%			
2	Making someone feel heard on time helps mapping out the process on the organization.	420	248	69	40	25	802	3.75	1.368	Agree
		84	62	23	20	25	214			
		39.3	29.0	10.7	9.3	11.7	100%			
3	Timely exchanging of ideas help tracks results.	470	188	87	26	31	802	3.75	1.438	Agree
		94	47	29	13	31	214			
		43.9	22.0	13.6	6.1	14.5	100%			
4	On time sharing of knowledge promotes searching for opportunities.	495	184	93	24	26	823	3.84	1.382	Agree
		99	46	31	12	26	214			
		46.3	21.5	14.5	5.6	12.1	100%			
5	Receiving and understanding with clarity and purpose helps selling products to a new group of customers.	380	180	141	20	36	757	3.54	1.439	Agree
		76	45	47	10	36	214			
		35.5	21.0	22.0	4.7	16.8	100%			
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.762	1.389	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1, 166 respondents out of 214 representing 77.6 percent agreed that prompt listening for information helps the business allocate resources 3.93 and standard deviation of 1.316. Making someone feel heard on time helps mapping out the process on the organization 146 respondents representing 77.6 percent agreed with mean score of 3.75 and standard deviation of 1.368. Timely exchanging of ideas help tracks results 141 respondents representing 65.9 percent agreed with mean score of 3.75 and standard deviation of 1.438. On time sharing of knowledge promotes searching for opportunities 145 respondents representing 67.8 percent agreed with mean score of 3.84 and 1.382. Receiving and understanding with clarity and purpose helps selling products to a new group of customers 121 respondents representing 56.5 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.54 and standard deviation 1.439

Test of Hypotheses

Promptly and effectively addressing tasks has effect on the sales increase of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state

Table 2: Z – Test Kolmogorov on promptly and effectively addressing tasks has effect on the sales increase of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test						
		Being responsible improve work relationships and increase the number of sales.	Enhancing professional performance promoted the growth of the business.	Boosting the well-being at work enhanced contact of customers.	Fulfilling commitments increased success in the business.	Learning from mistakes improved growth in revenue in the organizations.
N		214	214	214	214	214
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.502	.554	.540	.488	.530
	Positive	.121	.084	.065	.079	.103
	Negative	-.502	-.554	-.540	-.488	-.530
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		7.349	8.100	7.895	7.143	7.759
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
a. Test distribution is Uniform.						
b. Calculated from data.						

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value of $7.143 < 8.100$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that promptly and effectively addressing tasks had positive significant effect on the sales increase of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value of $7.143 < 8.100$ against the critical Z- value of .000 (2-tailed test at 97percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that promptly and effectively addressing tasks had positive significant effect on the sales increase of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state

Timely communication has effect on the market development of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Table 3: Z – Test Kolmogorov on timely communication has effect on the market development of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test						
		Prompt listening for information helps the business allocate resources.	Making someone feel heard on time helps mapping out the process on the organisation.	Timely exchanging of ideas help tracks results.	On time sharing of knowledge promotes searching for opportunities.	Receiving and understanding with clarity and purpose helps selling products to a new group of customers.
N		214	214	214	214	214
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.526	.432	.439	.463	.355
	Positive	.117	.117	.145	.121	.168
	Negative	-.526	-.432	-.439	-.463	-.355
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		7.690	6.323	6.426	6.768	5.195
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
a. Test distribution is Uniform.						
b. Calculated from data.						

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value of $5.195 < 7.690$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that timely communication had significant positive effect on the market development of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value of $5.195 < 7.690$ against the critical Z- value of .000 (2-tailed test at 97percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that timely communication had significant positive effect on the market development of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state

Discussions of Findings

Promptly and effectively addressing tasks had positive significant effect on the sales increase of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state

Hypotheses one revealed that comparing the calculated Z- value of $7.143 < 8.100$ against the critical Z- value of $.000$ (2-tailed test at 97percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that promptly and effectively addressing tasks had positive significant effect on the sales increase of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state. In line with these hypotheses, Didia, Akani & Ateke (2023) The purpose of this study is to investigate pricing strategies and sales force performance in food and beverages firms in Port Harcourt. The study employed a descriptive survey as its research design. The population of this study was twenty-three (23) registered food and beverages firms in Port Harcourt. The study found that pricing strategies positively and significantly influences sales performance of food and beverages firms in Port Harcourt. Based on the findings, the study therefore concluded pricing strategies significantly influences sales force performance of food and beverages firms in Port Harcourt.

Timely communication had significant positive effect on the market development of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State

These hypotheses, reveals that, comparing the calculated Z- value of $5.195 < 7.690$ against the critical Z- value of $.000$ (2-tailed test at 97percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that timely communication had significant positive effect on the market development of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state. In line with these, Nwonyuku (2016) conducted a study on the goal of a firm is to create sustainable profitability. This study was aimed to explore the relationship between corporate governance and profitability of firms, employing eight food and beverages firms listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange from 2004 to 2014. The data were analyzed using basic descriptive and inferential statistics with Ordinary Least Square multiple regression in a panel data setting. The results revealed that at 5 per cent level of significance, board size has positive relationship with return on equity and net assets per share. However, board composition has negative relationship with return on equity but with positive association with net assets per share.

Summary of Findings

- i. Promptly and effectively addressing tasks had positive significant effect on the sales increase of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state $Z(95, n = 214), 7.143 < 8.100, P. < .05$.
- ii. Timely communication had significant positive effect on the market development of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state $Z(95, n = 214), 5.195 < 7.690, P. < .05$.

Conclusion

The study concluded that promptly and effectively addressing tasks and timely communication had significant effect on the sales increase and market development of food and beverage firms in Enugu State. Building sustainable organizations in the complex and rapidly changing environment of today is demanding bold new management strategies from leaders. Responsiveness is a valuable skill for developing a sustainable business model that creates value, solves problems, and fosters customer loyalty. Promptly addressing customer inquiries, providing clear and concise answers, and actively seeking feedback are effective strategies for being responsive to customers.

Recommendation

- i. The management of food and beverage firms should try and break the workload into manageable chunks and setting priorities to helps break the cycle of missed deadlines, last-minute rushes, and procrastination.
- ii. For effectiveness there is need for the organizations to give to the employees the right information at the right time which will increase the organizational productivity and also helps build momentum, making it easier to tackle the remaining tasks.

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